

Synthetic Methods and Reactions[†]

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This review describes the development of new synthetic transformations using simple and inexpensive reagents such as halotrimethylsilanes, nickel boride, trityl tetrafluoroborate, Cd^{II}, Sn^{II} and Cu^{II} salts and magnesium. Generally natural products have been used as substrates to demonstrate the utility of the new methodology.

The past three decades have witnessed the development of a large number of new synthetic methods and reactions and this subject has partly been dealt within an elegant monograph entitled, 'Comprehensive organic functional group transformations'¹. Over the years our group has been engaged in developing new synthetic transformations using inexpensive reagents so that their utility in industrial processes could be exploited. The development of new synthetic transformations is important as the success of any total synthesis of a complex target molecule depends upon the judicious use of this armoury (i.e. new synthetic methods) in the presence of other sensitive functionalities.

This review gives a concise account of our new synthetic methodology developed during the past one-and-half decades.

Deoxygenation of vic-diol :

The occurrence of vic-diol group in many biologically active molecules and especially in carbohydrates has necessitated its transformation into the corresponding olefin for various reasons. Two elegant methods for this transformation have been described by Corey and Hopkins² and Barrett *et al.*³ (equations 1 and 2 respectively, Scheme 1).

We found that sec-tert vic-diols can be easily and efficiently deoxygenated using iodotrimethylsilane (ITMS) generated *in situ* from chlorotrimethylsilane (CTMS) and sodium iodide in CH₃CN at 0° in 5–10 min (equation 3)⁴.

However, bis-sec vic-diols were found to be inert under these conditions and also at reflux temperature (equation 4)⁵. Interestingly, allylic bis-sec vic-diols underwent this transformation smoothly to the corresponding dienes (equation 5)⁵. Again, the tert-prim vic-diol was found to be inert to this reagent combination (equation 6). However, the corresponding iodohydrin was smoothly transformed into the olefin as demonstrated in the conversion of calliterpenone to phyllocladen-3-one (equation 7)⁶. The conversion of tert-sec vic-diols to olefins is stereospecific as demonstrated by us in the synthesis of several sesquiterpene lactones (equation 8)⁷ (Scheme 2).

[†] Respectfully dedicated to Dr. Sukh Dev for his outstanding contribution to organic chemistry and to commemorate his 75th birthday.

Deoxygenation of *vic*-diols has also been achieved with *p*-TsOH and sodium iodide⁸.

Deoxygenation of epoxides :

Iodotrimethylsilane (ITMS) generated *in situ* from chlorotrimethylsilane (CTMS) and sodium iodide in CH₃CN deoxygenates the epoxides efficiently under mild reaction conditions^{9,10}. We observed that hydroiodic acid generated *in situ* from *p*-TSOH/NaI¹¹ or TFA/NaI¹² deoxygenates the epoxides in excellent yield. However, in case of arteannuin B (1), a rearranged product annulide (2) was obtained using any one of the above mentioned reagents¹³ (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

Reductive removal of *tert*-hydroxy group in an α,β -unsaturated- γ -*tert*-hydroxy ketones :

Generally this transformation (equation 9) is achieved using zinc-AcOH under refluxing conditions. The reaction of several substrates with *in situ* generated iodotrimethylsilane (ITMS) in CH₃CN gave the corresponding α,β -unsaturated ketone in excellent yield at room temperature¹⁴. However, the reaction of 6 α -hydroxycholest-4-en-3-one (3) gave cholestan-3,6-dione (4) as the sole product in quantitative yield. A similar transformation (equation 10) was later reported by Hartman and Curley¹⁵ (Scheme 4).

Silicon mediated *C*-isoprenylation of phenols :

Isoprenyl unit is present in several biologically active phenolic compounds as such or in a modified form. Its introduction at the *ortho*-position in a phenolic compound is generally achieved under basic conditions¹⁶ using 3,3-dimethyl allyl bromide and NaOCH₃, and under acidic conditions using 2-methyl-but-3-ene-2-ol/BF₃¹⁷. We achieved this transformation (equation 11) using isoprene and iodotrimethylsilane under almost neutral conditions¹⁸ (Scheme 5).

Partial steroidal structure represents the molecule belonging to the cholestane series.

Scheme 4

Scheme 5

Cyclodehydrogenation of *ortho*-(3,3-dimethyl allyl)-phenols :

Trityl tetrafluoroborate (TTFB) is well known for its ability to abstract hydride ion from the sufficiently basic carbon atoms and we exploited this property for the cyclodehydrogenation reaction (equation 12). This transformation is generally carried out using DDQ in benzene under refluxing conditions. The advantage of TTFB over DDQ is the selectivity of the former where the chromane type compounds do not undergo dehydrogenation (equation 13)¹⁹ (Scheme 6).

Cleavage of ethers :

Deprotection of MTM ethers :

Methylthiomethyl (MTM) ether is an excellent protect-

Scheme 6

ing group for the hydroxyl group especially the tertiary hydroxyl as the preparation of the same can be carried out in excellent yield under mild reaction conditions (DMSO-Ac₂O-AcOH at r.t.)²⁰. MTM ethers are stable under normal acidic and basic conditions. Their deprotection has been achieved using TTFB at room temperature and the yields of the alcohols obtained are excellent (equation 14)²¹. The earlier methods employed mercuric salts in acetonitrile-water²². Nickel boride reduction of the MTM ethers has resulted in the formation of the corresponding methyl ethers²³ (Scheme 7).

Scheme 7

tert-MTM ethers have been cleaved with CTMS/Ac₂O to yield the corresponding acetoxymethyl ethers in excellent yields (5 → 6a) which can be converted to the corresponding alcohols under mild acidic or basic conditions (6a → 6b) (Scheme 8). Acetoxymethyl ethers were also prepared in 75–78% yield when MTM ethers were treated with Hg(OAc)₂/MeCN. When this reaction was carried out in presence of H₂O, the corresponding alcohol was obtained in 95% yield²⁴. The reaction of MTM ethers with HgCl₂ in the presence of 2-(methoxy)ethanol, methanol and ethanol furnished the corresponding MEM, MOM and EOM ethers respectively²⁵.

Methyl and benzyl ethers have been converted to the corresponding acetates with a combination of reagents consisting of CTMS and Ac₂O containing a catalytic amount of conc. H₂SO₄²⁶.

Scheme 8

Some applications of nickel boride :

Reductive removal of an allylic functional group :

This transformation is very useful while working on the synthesis of complex natural products or their structure elucidation. Nickel boride reductivity cleaves the carbon-oxygen single bond at the allylic position (Scheme 9) and the ease of cleavage has been found to be OCOCF₃ > OCOCH₃ > OSiMe₃ > OH > OCH₃^{27,28}. This is one of the excellent method for the preparation of cholest-4-ene from cholesterol.

In some cases the reductive removal of the allylic group is attended by double bond migration whereas in others the db gets reduced or both. Apparently in the last case, first the reductive removal of the allylic group takes place followed by reduction of the double bond²⁹.

Boar *et al.*³⁰ reported that the reaction of dithioacetals with nickel boride furnishes the olefins in good yield. The nickel boride reduction of allylic dithioacetals did not give

Scheme 9

the dienes as expected but the corresponding olefins by reductive removal of the functional group³¹.

Scheme 10

α -Halo ketones and *vic*-dibromides are converted into the corresponding ketones and alkenes respectively with the *in situ* generated nickel boride³².

Conversion of azides to amines :

A host of reagents are known for the conversion of azides to amines. It was observed by us that azides can be converted into amines in excellent yield by reduction with Ni_2B generated *in situ* from $NaBH_4$ and $NiCl_2 \cdot 6H_2O$ ³³.

Nickel boride affects the conversion of allylic hydroperoxides and peroxides to the corresponding alcohols and ethers respectively in excellent yield^{34,35}.

It has also been demonstrated that *in situ* generated nickel boride is an excellent reagent for deoxymercuration³⁶ (Scheme 11).

Scheme 11

Transformation of vinyl nitro compounds into carbonyl compounds and α -hydroxycarbonyl compounds :

According to Olah *et al.*³⁷ tert-nitro compounds give iodides with iodotrimethylsilane (ITMS), secondary nitro compounds undergo deoxygenation to the corresponding oximes, primary nitro compounds undergo dehydration to the nitriles (Scheme 12).

Scheme 12

To complete the story, we studied the reaction of vinyl nitro and allylic nitro compounds with *in situ* generated ITMS.

Vinyl nitro compounds react rapidly with iodotrimethylsilane or its *in situ* equivalent (CTMS/NaI) at 0–5° to provide the corresponding carbonyl compounds as the major products, the minor products being the corresponding keto oximes and α -hydroxy ketones³⁸. Stannous iodide also reacts with vinyl nitro compounds to give the corresponding carbonyl compounds³⁹ (Scheme 13).

Scheme 13

Other reagents which have been used to effect this transformation are $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ - Mg - H_2O system⁴⁰ and Zn - TFA /organic solvent⁴¹.

Reaction of vinyl nitro compounds with excess $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ provides the corresponding α -hydroxy ketones in excellent yield⁴², the minor product being the α -hydroxy oxime (Scheme 14). This is the first application of the water of crystallization present in the inorganic salt.

Scheme 14

Conversion of allylic nitro compounds to α,β -unsaturated ketones :

Allylic nitro compounds can be converted into α,β -unsaturated ketones with excess $\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in excellent yield⁴³, the minor product being the corresponding alcohol (Scheme 15). This strategy can be used to build the corticosteroid side chain from 17-keto steroids.

Scheme 15

Synthesis of vinyl nitro compounds :

Vinyl nitro compounds are generally prepared by the Henry reaction in which the carbonyl compound is condensed with an alkyl nitro compound and the resulting α -hydroxy nitro compound is subjected to dehydration conditions. Several methods have been reported for the dehydration of α -hydroxy nitro compounds. We carried out this dehydration using triphenyl phosphine and carbon tetrachloride in the presence of a catalytic amount of dry triethylamine^{44a}. The

yields are excellent and interestingly the products obtained are having exclusively *E*-configuration^{44b} (equation 15) (Scheme 16). We also observed that anhydrous CuSO_4 adsorbed on silica gel is an efficient reagent for the dehydration of α -hydroxynitro compounds⁴⁵. Retro-Henry reaction of cyclic 2-nitro alcohols with this reagent leads to the synthesis of ketonitroaliphatic compounds⁴⁵ which is a reaction of great synthetic utility (equation 16) (Scheme 16).

Scheme 16

Olefins react with CTMS and NaNO_2 in CH_2Cl_2 to furnish the chloronitro derivatives in good yields⁴⁶ (Scheme 17) which can be dehydrohalogenated to the corresponding vinyl nitro compounds.

Scheme 17

Allylation of carbonyl compounds :

Allylation of carbonyl compounds is a reaction of immense synthetic utility and several procedures are reported. We made use of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and Mg in THF to achieve this transformation⁴⁷ (equation 17, Scheme 18). This reagent combination also reduces the aldehydes to the corresponding alcohols when a small amount of water is added slowly into the reaction medium (equation 18). It has also been demonstrated that tin(II) chloride dihydrate-magnesium in THF is a useful system for effecting allylation of carbonyl compounds at room temperature⁴⁸.

Dithioacetalization and its reverse transformation :

Formation of dithioacetals from carbonyl compounds and their reverse transformation is often required in complex synthesis. It was observed by us that dithioacetals can be prepared efficiently using anhydrous CuSO_4 in THF and the reverse transformation can be effected by $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

contrary claims have been made due to oversight of our results^{60,61}.

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